

Handling Some Syntax Functions of the Infinitive and other Irregular Forms of the Northern Dialect from the First Grammar (Syntax) of the Albanian Language

Linguistics

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Abstract

This research wants to show the syntactical function of the infinitive and the other unchangeable form of the northern dialect in the folkloric creation. This issue has been discussed scientifically from different foreign and Albanian researchers such as: Lambertz, A. Xhuvani, I. Sheperi, K. cipoetc, in different grammar books during the years. It should be said that these constructions, at times they are called clauses, sometimes called the sentence. They usually go directly, but sometimes with connecting words or linkers. Sometimes they are functionally equivalent to verbal sentences with verb in subjunctive replaceable them, so functionally synonymous with different dependent sentences. M. Celek concludes that today's Albanian literary language has not existed as many of the European languages, as is the northern dialect of Albanian. Gerund of the northern dialect which is a realistic concept of the true meaning of the word, fully comparable in all directions with the gerund of other languages, carries over 12 key syntax functions.

Note: Some of the folkloric phrases of the Albanian language do not express the same connotation and there is no equivalent in English so they have been used in the original form of the Albanian language.

The issue raised for scientific discussion in terms of irregular forms in our language presents two views: one belongs to the period before World War II and is mainly related to the names of grammarians who compiled the first textbooks of pre-university education, in which the verbal forms without themselves (as may be called) are known as predictability; for example:

*U tha dajavet, dilni jashtë/
Si me pasë kullën me kashtë;*¹³ Ose:

*O Tahir i biri i trimit/
Ç'i ke ba ti armët florinit?/
I kam vjerrë nën gem t'ullinit/
Me i lshue rrexe t'gjith Ulqinit.*¹⁴

(where the conditional relations in the first clause and second phrase in the second, and those in the second, are constructed by means of the northern dialect “to have” and “to let” - compare: as if it had, in order to release them); the other period occupies the time after, to nowadays for example, in the following verses, all the non-ideal forms: two participles and two infinitives of the northern dialect in the Grammar of the Albanian Language (otherwise, of the Academy of Sciences of Albania) in the analysis of functional division, are placed in the order of the second syntax categories: two circumstantial ways and two circumstantial purposes:

*Si m'ka dalun buka mue?/
Paa pjekë e paa kullue/*

Mos me u ngranë, mos me u kerkue.

And in the passage of an erotic song, recorded by Kasem Taipi, in the collection "Popular Zana"⁹¹ the irregular form of the 4th verse, provided with the predicate, by having a noun in the main function:

Syt'e mij tue kja s'pushojnë,
 porsì çesme, porsì krue,
 sado mot, moj, qi do t'shkojnë,
 ahti* i emka me t'mundue."⁹²

Or from our national epic of Visar of the Nation, collected from Palajt and Kurti, we found:

“Ka qitë Muji e ka thanë:/
 - Gja kjo andërr mos me kallxue,
 Kurr ma andr'et s'kam me i besue;”⁹³

That negative form of “mos me kallxue” behaves as the predecessor of the second verse, because it has subject “kjoandërr”, while the other “s'kam me i besue” of the second syntax function of the words, while its subject, for born native speakers, it is clearly distinguished from the “kam” - the first / singular verb. In folk creativity there are few instances that the negative form of the predictability of irregular forms, such as infinitive in the northern dialect comes in very complicated and difficult to interpret, as in the following case.

“Pushka e trimitpokerset//Ku t'qillojnë// t'ban me dekë,”⁹⁴ - where the verb “me dekë”, only circumstantial purpose cannot be in any way; in the simplest judgment, it relates to the subject-subject (SN) “pushka e trimit” - the headline of subject in this phrase.

Handling the issue from grammatics, (syntax) of the first Albanian language

The syntax of Albanian studies has started firstly by foreigners. It was the albanologist Max Lambertz, who 103 years ago, produced in German the monograph known as "Die Hypothetische Periode im Albanischen", (Hypothetical Period in Albanian),⁹⁵ published in the magazine "Ingogermanische Forschungen", 1914-1915, Volume 34, p. 44-208, in which the author, among other things, deals with the formation of the conditional sentences with infinitive in northern dialect “*me ba me..., me kenë se...*”), relying on that little literature that was in circulation

⁹¹Taipi, Kasem. Zana popullore, Tiranë 1933, f. 4

⁹²Taipi, Kasem. Këngë popullore shkodrane (Mbledhës të Folklorit 11, Tiranë, 1998, f. 61.

⁹³Palaj, Ât Benardin – Kurti, Ât Donat. Visaret e Kombit, Vëllimi II, Kangë Kreshnikësh dhe legjenda, Tiranë Shtypshkroja “Nikaj”, 1937, f. 163. *aht-i, psherëtimë-a.

⁹⁴Vincens, P. Visari Komtaar, Kangë popullore gëgnishte, Sarajevo, 1911, Druck und Verlag von Daniel A. Kajon, f. 52.

⁹⁵Lambertz, Max. Periudha hipotetike në gjuhën shqipe (Përkthyer nga Veniamin Dashi), Botimet Albanologjike, Tiranë, 2011. (Përgatitur për botim nga T.Topalli e E.Malaj).

in his time, such as singing books published by Vienna's "Dija" society, Kristoforidh's works, and Curian's publicity.⁹⁶

In other cases of this argument, he also used folkloric materials collected from Prennush, poetry of Fishta and writings from the Albanian diaspora, as well as Konica's "Albania" magazine, without leaving out the basic works of Bogdan, Kamardë, Naim, Sami, Meyri, Pedersen, GjergjPekmez, SotirGurra, and others. We can say that, in the theoretical plan, the treatment of the predictability of infinitive forms in the northern dialect is done for the first time in our language. Specifically, it should be noted that the collection from the popular composing of VincensPrennushit's "VisarKomtar" was probably a search of a prominent Austrian albanologist in the field of popular syntax, not only for the reality of constructing hypothetical relationships with the northern dialect but also other reports, as we can bring from it the final purposesentence patterns:

E bukura ndejë në qoshk	- Heqim kurr, mor, mos u gjetët
U rrezosh e rash teposhtë,	Ty s'të la, more, <u>me m'prekë</u> ;
E thesh kamen e thesh gjun'	Kurr heqim mos u gjetët për mue
Heqim-bash t'u basha un.	Ty s'të la <u>me m'heqimue</u> . ⁹⁷

One year after this monograph, in 1916, didactic and renowned activity of Albanian education, Gaspert Mikeli,⁹⁸ publishes the textbook "Grammar of the Albanian language", in which the syntax extends from page 125 - 135; there are models of constructing sentences with infinitive in the northern dialect such as: *Me qeshë kendin paa arsye /âsht shnjëzim. Kshtu /n'vënd qi me thanë /dielli shndritë, /thona /hana shndritë. Me bâ analizën logjike t'njaj foljes/ don me thanë /me e vrejtn /se ç'farë foljet âsht... /me diftue ndertimin e sajë /si dhe me kerkue imtas pjesët e para t'sajat /qi e perbajnë. Hanibali shestoj planin/ me shkapërcye Alpet me ushtrina t'veta /dhe me shtrue Romën.⁹⁹* - where you can clearly distinguish the key functions, subject, object, and goals of northern dialect. Six more years will be spent in 1922 when other textbooks of Albanian syntax by albanologist Aleksandër Xhuvani who started to draft and publish, a text for secondary education, which was reprinted in 1938, where the author makes steps forward in the treatment not only the non-existent we are talking about, but also categorically delivers terminology of sentence separation; Thus, in the presentation of the main sentences we know the division into two groups:

- a. in sentences that are constructed infinitive forms and which are called unedited and
- b. sentences constructed in other ways, called edited sentence example:

Duhet /me u dalë zot të vorfënvët. Kush ban mirë, /gjen mirë. Lypset/ me folë me vend,/ ase mos me folë fare. In this line the author goes on to the sentence of the object (counterpart), when

⁹⁶Po ai, po aty, f. 211-212

⁹⁷Vincens, Prennushi. Visari Komtaar, Kangë popullore gegnishte, Sarajevo, 1911, Druck und Verlag von Daniel A.Kajon, f. 123.

⁹⁸Mikeli, Gasper. Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe, Shtypshkronja "Nikaj", Shkodër, 1916.

⁹⁹Po ai, po aty, f. 131 - 133.

using such examples: *Dishroj /me bamë një udhëtim kësaj vere. I miri nuk din me ba keq.*¹⁰⁰ This division in edited sentences and unedited sentences, Xhuvani has also saved it for periodic with sentences that expresses time, place, goal, causes, concretized with examples of predictability in infinitive of the northern forms.¹⁰¹ This phenomenon is also noted in the "grammar and syntax" of the Albanian language" (especially the southern dialect, for high schools) of Ilia Dilo Sheperi,¹⁰² where the author begins with the expression of relationship with infinitive of the northern dialect. such as: */me qenë i urtë, kishë me fitue shumë, /me dhanë fjalën, duhet me e mbajtë. duke treguar se "dialekti toskërisht në vend të paskajores përdor mënyrën lidhore."*¹⁰³ Sheperi, too, does not fail to point out that for the construction of goal sentences, both dialectal forms can be used such as: *Përgatitet për të shkuar (ose për me shkue) Vete të punojë (ose me punue).*¹⁰⁴ This infinitive, in predicative functions is widely expressed by a linguist Justin Rrota,¹⁰⁵ in the well-known "Syntax of Albanian" work, in 1942, to express the sentences of the subject, the sentences of the object, as well as many sentence phrases, provided with numerous and so natural examples of Albanian language, such as: *Nuk asht mirë kurr, me vum gojë mbë të Parë, Kush nuk din me heshtë, nuk din me folë, Dallëndyshet kthejnë ndër ne, si të nisë me dalë pranvera, Edhe të më kishesh pvetë, un lanë me shkue nuk të kishem. Mendo përpara në daç mos me u pendue mbrapa, etj.*

In his work, the linguist Kostaq Cipo,¹⁰⁶ 1952, analyzes subordinate sentences, without classifying the unit of the period as a separate part, p. 86 and, in presenting the predicate phrases of the phrase, completely excludes the use of infinitive in the northern dialect in the expression of predicates; for unedited sentences, it gives examples only with the "përtë + pjesore (participle)" which is also the standard of nowadays. The last text we have reviewed in the first place is the book "Grammar of Albanian Language", Part Two - Syntax - Text for seven-year schools and high schools, compiled by prof. Mahir Domi¹⁰⁷ in 1954, but published as a textbook in 1957. We think that with this book, the lesson closes a phase of our syntactic studies to continue with a higher level in the scientific point of view not only of the syntactic functional categories but also of the components of the period, without leaving aside an elaborate terminology and quite unified.¹⁰⁸

Knowledge about the period is provided by p. 131 - 215 and throughout this division, the author pays special attention to the predictability of unchanged forms. In & 2 of p. 132, the author has put a note that applies to all sentences of phrases, both in prepaid and hypothetical mergers, especially: "Verbs' sentences of a period may be either in one of their own ways and numbers (such as the conditional and the subjective form and the special Albanian forms of urdherore,

¹⁰⁰Xhuvani, A. Sintaksa shqip, Pjesë e dytë, për klasët e ulta të shkollave të mesme, Shtëpia Botonjësë "Kristo Luarasi", Tiranë, 1938.

¹⁰¹Po ai, po aty, f. 33 – 38

¹⁰²Sheperi, I.D. Gramatika e dhe Sindaksa e gjuhës shqipe – Sidomos e toskënishtes, për shkollat e mesme, Vlorë, më 1927.

¹⁰³Po ai, po aty, f. 167.

¹⁰⁴Po ai, po aty, f. 174.

¹⁰⁵Rrota, J. Sintaksi i shqipes – Për klasën II, III, IV të shkollave të mesme- Pranue prej Ministris s' Arsimit me shkresën Nr. 224/11, d. 11-11-1942 – XX, Shkodër, Shtypshkroja "At Gjergj Fishta" - 1942-XX.

¹⁰⁶Cipo, K. Sintaksa, Instituti i Shkencave, Tiranë, 1952.

¹⁰⁷Domi, M. Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe, Pjesa e dytë, Sintaksa, Tekst për shkollat shtatëvjeçare e shkollat e mesme, Botim i tretë, Botim i Ministrisë s' Arsimit dhe Kulturës, Tiranë, 1957.

¹⁰⁸Topalli, T. Kurs leksionesh për sintaksologët shqiptarë në programin pasuniversitar "Master", U.Sh., 2010-2011.

deshirore, habitore, defto)they are called edited sentences or in one of the ways that have the same form for all of them, both in singular and in plural, such as(infinitive and participle) and then referred to as unedited sentences. Verbs of infinitive and participle take them as a predicate of a special sentence, as an only sentence when we can turn them into edited sentences. For example, Do të dal në pazar **për të blerë qershi** (= që të blej qershi). **Duke shkuar rrugës** (= ndërsa shkoja rrugës), pashë tët vëlla.

These verbs can sometimes be taken as part of the sentence (subject, object, complement) rather than as separate sentences, especially when they are unaccompanied by other words, from other parts of the sentence. For example, in the period: *S'asht mirë me u ngutë* – paskajoren *me u ngutë* mund ta marrim si kryefjalë të foljes *s'asht mirë*.¹⁰⁹

In addition to this very important scientific information, for many subordinate sentences, the author has dealt with the use as predicates of all unedited forms as determinative, temporal, causal, purpose, conditional, and the Albanian special forms of mënyrore, rrjedhore, lejore, in which infinitive of the northern dialect has special form and occupies a special place. In other works, compiled in the years to come, there were revisions, new attitudes of linguists and scholars to the problem of predicate, expressed in unformed forms, while in the normative grammar of Albanian,¹¹⁰ publication of ASHSH, part II, 1997, the group of drafting authors has maintained the following stance: "Questionable and unequal solution is in syntax the value of constructions with unedited verbal forms, such as: infinitive, gerund, participle, (See also the header "Verb"). These forms have no grammatically expressed categories of themselves, their numbers, the way and the time, so there have been and have different attitudes regarding their ability to be predicated, the organizational center of sentences. Constructions with gerund, some constructions with participle, sometimes with infinitive in the grammar of some languages are taken as some sort of ordinate sentences. So it was also done in our previous grammatical tradition, in which they are called" subordinate unedited clauses". But since they do not possess the category of modality, the main feature of the predicate in many grammatical constructions with them the value of the sentence has been denied and are taken as clause of sentences. Sometimes they are treated differently according to specific circumstances in some cases they are taken as sentences, in other cases as clauses.¹¹¹ It should be said that these constructions, at times they are called clauses, sometimes called the sentence. They usually go directly, but sometimes with connecting words or linkers. Sometimes they are functionally equivalent to verbal sentences with verb in subjunctive replaceable them, so functionally synonymous with different dependent sentences. *“Për këtë arsye, ndërtimë me trajtat e pashtjelluara, kur kanë kryefjalë të veçantë të shprehur, është e përligjur të merren si fjali të varura. Po ashtu, me ndonjë rezervë, kur janë mjaftësisht të zgjeruara e të zëvendësueshme, pa ndonjë vështirësi, me fjali të ndryshme të varura mund të merren si ndërtimë sinonimike me këto fjali e të studiohen krahas tyre.”*¹¹²

¹⁰⁹Po ai, po aty, f. 132-133.

¹¹⁰ASHRSH, IGJ dhe IL, Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe II, Tiranë, 1997.

¹¹¹Po aty, f. 489 – 490.

¹¹²Po aty, f. 489 – 490.

In order to close this chronological presentation of the status of gerund in the northern dialect generally speaking, we have to emphasize that, for nearly 20 years, our linguistics has been based on two detailed works compiled by M. Celiku¹¹³ and Tafil Kelmendi¹¹⁴ (as a Post Office). The first, elaborating on the gerund structure, has not expanded into the role of gerund in the northern dialect but ends in the conclusion. “*se gjuha e sotme shqipe nuk ka paskajore të mirëfilltë, të krahasueshme me paskajoret e gjuhëve të tjera dhe me paskajoren e gegërishtes me punue.*”¹¹⁵ This author, in 1999, publishes a special study, “The syntactic status of unedited forms and constructions formed with them”¹¹⁶ where, in some ways, the author maintains another attitude towards gerund of the northern dialect appreciating the legacy of tradition, outlined by many linguists of the first half of the XX century and focusing on this unedited form; Celiku said: “But there is also another kind of independent gerund. This gerund corresponds to a predicate, while she itself is not a preaching center.”¹¹⁷ Next to the Albanian, he also gives models in Russian: *Me punue mirë është detyra jonë./ Rabotat horosho – nasha zadaça.*

Further, M. Celek concludes that today's Albanian literary language has not existed as many of the European languages, as is the northern dialect of Albanian. Gerund of the northern dialect which is a realistic concept of the true meaning of the word, fully comparable in all directions with the gerund of other languages, carries over 12 key syntax functions.¹¹⁸ But the work that agrees and is totally in support of our work (including the extensive treatment of the doctoral thesis) is the monograph by T. Kelmendi “Synthesistic functions of the gerund in Albanian language (According to folklore)”¹¹⁹ Just to say two parts from Chapter IV, p. 91 “Gerund in object function”- separated by the author with the titles “Gerund with verbs and phrasal verbs in lexical meaning in speaking (verbaloquenda) and “Gerund with verbs and phrasal verbs in lexical meaning in understanding (verbacomunicandi),”¹²⁰ to be convinced in the multitude of this gerund in the northern dialect in oral creativity, seen from the point of view of the folk syntax, the field where the chosen thesis is also assigned to me. With examples and persuasive models, the new linguist Kelmendi has a valuable help in the field of the Albanian syntax, or of the national visitor in prose and poetry; as for objective functions and goals etc..

A t'kamthanëmos me ardhë ma përpara.Po mëthërrasin me shkue. Po bërtetukisamunet me jashliruekamenprejlisit. I çon fjalënjiharap me dalë me babejleg, poishteplak.

Letermbretinakashkrue, / ShaqirGrishen me e rrethue.

Even from the Epic of Kreshniks, Kelmendi brings poetic constructions like:¹²¹

Paj Halili tu beg-ja ka mrrri,/

¹¹³Celiku, M.Format e pashtjelluara të foljes në gjuhën shqipe, shulu, Tiranë, 2000; ribotim më, 2006.

¹¹⁴Kelmendi, T. Instituti Albanologjik, Funkcionet sintaksore të ndërtimeve me paskajore në gjuhën shqipe, Prishtinë, 2010.

¹¹⁵Celiku, M.Format e pashtjelluara të foljes në gjuhën shqipe, shblu, Tiranë, 2000; ribotim në vitin 2006, f. 225.

¹¹⁶Celiku, M. Statusi sintaksor i formave të pështjell. dhe i ndërtimeve me to”, SF/1999, 3-4, f. 53 – 68.

¹¹⁷Po ai, po aty, f. 61.

¹¹⁸Po ai, po aty, f. 61. (Pohimin e fundit, autori ynë e sjell të cituar nga gjuhëtari kosovar Tafil Kelmendi – shkëputur nga punimi i magjistraturës, 1980, 277 faqe.)

¹¹⁹Instituti Albanologjik, Kelmendi, T., **Funksionet sintaksore të ndërtimeve me paskajore në gjuhën shqipe**” (Sipas folklorit), Prishtinë, 2010

¹²⁰Po ai, po aty, f. 91 – 98.

¹²¹Po ai, po aty, f. 91 – 98.

Me mahmuza gjogun po ma ther/
Edhe frenin mirë ja ke shtërngue,
Po i jep shenjë, tha, gjogut *me hingëllue*.
(Këngë kreshnike I, 22)

Martin Camaj, who in 1984 compiled the book "Albanian Grammar",¹²² also uses the conjunction along with the northern dialect (as he did in his literary production in prose and poetry), but also other forms of unedited prediction, as in the following examples: *me i ikë rrezikut nuk asht ligështi, por urti; me u ba i zoti i vetes, lypet prej çdo të riut; e pau duke shkuar rrugës; si ka mujtë me i ra në të, se unë jam grue e jo burrë; për pa vdekë, s'kam për ta harrue, grueja i la një vajzë me ia pasë lakmi gjithkush; ishte i vocërr, qi me m'zi me e pa; pa mos thanë një, nuk bahen dy*¹²³ etj.

¹²²Camaj, M. Albanian Grammar, with Exercises Chrestomathy and Glossaries, Collaborated on and translated by Leonard Fox, Otto Harrassovitz-Wiesbaden, 1984.

¹²³ Po ai, po aty, f. 246-247.